

Resolution Booklet

1st Small Scale Event for University Students

Motion for a Resolution by the Committee on Women's Rights and Gender Equality (FEMM)

Cry for help: Domestic violence has elevated during lockdown with the European Commission noting a dramatic increase in reports by 60% around Europe. How can the EU protect women's human rights and gender equality during a pandemic?

Inês Camposinhos (PT), Francesca Saletta (IT), Francis Stefanos (CY, Chairperson)

The European Youth Parliament,

- A. Deeply concerned that [1 in 3 women](#) globally have been put through Intimate Partner Violence (IPV)¹,
- B. Alarmed by the fact that [Domestic Violence crimes](#) have risen at a 20% rate, due to the COVID-19 pandemic,
- C. Noting with regret that IPV survivors are often:
 - i. diagnosed with [Post Traumatic Stress Disorder \(PTSD\)](#)² that leads to panic attacks and substance abuse,
 - ii. forced to endure the [Social Stigma](#) that comes with domestic abuse,
- D. Fully supporting the United Nations' (UN)³ collaborative publication of the [RESPECT Women framework](#),
- E. Pointing out the difficulty of access to healthcare for victims of IPV due to the COVID-19 pandemic as a result of [hospitals and health facilities](#) shutting down to the public,
- F. Acknowledges the Center for Disease Control and Prevention's (CDC)⁴ findings stating that [1 in 5 homicide victims globally](#) are a result of IPV,
- G. Recognizes the World Health Organisation's (WHO)⁵ revelation that [38% of all murders](#) of women are committed by intimate partners,
- H. Taking into account the impact of the offense that domestic violence is according to [Article 1 of the UNC and Article 7 - Rome statute of the International Criminal Court](#);

¹ **Intimate Partner Violence (IPV)** describes physical violence, sexual violence, stalking, or psychological harm by a current or former partner or spouse that occurs among heterosexual or same-sex couples and does not require sexual intimacy.

² **Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)** is a mental illness that manifests itself following up traumatic experiences an individual has faced. This illness is strongly associated with symptoms such as vivid flashbacks, panic and/or anxiety attacks, substance abuse, among others.

³ **United Nations (UN)** is an intergovernmental organization that aims to maintain international peace and security, develop friendly relations among nations, achieve international cooperation, and be a centre for harmonizing the actions of nations.

⁴ **Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC)** is the national public health agency of the USA that aims in protecting America from health, safety and security threats, both foreign and inside the US.

⁵ **World Health Organisation (WHO)** is a bilateral agency of the United Nations composed of 194 Member States that strives to combat diseases and coordinate international health within the United Nations system.

1. Invites the Member States to follow [Slovakia and Italy's example](#) of providing hotlines that women can reach out to receive help in the case of IPV's;
2. Encourages the European Broadcasting Union (EBU)⁶ to promote the services of the [Women Against Violence Europe \(WAVE\)](#) organisations to further aid and provide female identifying individuals with resources and support after they have fallen victims of domestic abuse;
3. Calls upon the European Economic and Social Committee (EESC)⁷ to promote free medical and psychological support for all women that went through trauma and do not have the financial possibility to afford a medical bill;
4. Encourages the Directorate General on Education, Youth and Culture (DG-EAC)⁸ to implement education channels and institutions with activities providing awareness on IPV-related crimes;
5. Appeals to the European Parliament to follow [Portugal's example](#) regarding social security and provide financial support aimed towards the survival of IPV victims in need that reside within Member States;
6. Calls upon the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU)⁹ to guide the judicial bodies of each Member State into proper evaluation of IPV cases.

⁶ The **European Broadcasting Union (EBU)** is the world's leading alliance in public service media consisting of 115 members across 56 countries both inside and outside the European Union.

⁷ **The European Economic and Social Committee (EESC)** is an EU advisory body comprising representatives of workers' and employers' organisations and other interest groups. It issues opinions on EU issues to the European Commission, the Council of the EU and the European Parliament, thus acting as a bridge between the EU's decision-making institutions and EU citizens.

⁸ **The Commission's Directorate General for Education and Culture (DG-EAC)** is the executive branch of the European Union responsible for policy on education, culture, youth, languages, and sport. It supports these issues through a variety of projects and programmes, prominently through the Creative Europe and Erasmus+ projects.

⁹ **The Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU)** interprets EU law to make sure it is applied in the same way in all EU countries, and settles legal disputes between national governments and EU institutions.

Motion for a Resolution by the Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety (ENVI)

With the travel restrictions posed by the pandemic, a dramatic reduction in travel and economic activity has in consequence led to the energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions to have fallen sharply. Taking into account the 2030 climate and energy framework, what measures can the EU take to keep the low emissions and maintain a sustainable environment?

Mónica Carvalho (PT, Delegate), João Ferreira (PT, Delegate), Pedro Matos (PT, Chairperson)

The European Youth Parliament,

- A. Recognising that [climate change has a dramatic effect on the environment](#), leading to an acceleration in biodiversity loss,
 - B. Deeply concerned that [global warming](#) has reached 1°C above pre-industrial level and is expected to continue growing at a rate of approximately 0.2°C per decade,
 - C. Taking into consideration that the [global temperature](#) will only be about 0.01°C lower in 2030 as a consequence of the travel restrictions imposed by successive lockdowns in the past year,
 - D. Noting with regret that the current legislation implemented in the European Union (EU):
 - i. disproportionately affects lower-income groups,
 - ii. fails to target the biggest emitters of greenhouse gas emissions,
 - E. Alarmed by the [disparities in the commitments of tackling climate change](#) between the Member States, with countries like Poland expected to fall short of the greenhouse gas emissions goals for 2030, whilst countries like Sweden are on track to overachieve these targets,
 - F. Approving the [Recovery Plan for Europe](#) that intends to invest 373.9 billion euros in Natural Resources and the Environment,
 - G. Noting with satisfaction that the [legislative proposal for the European Climate Law](#) was submitted to the European Parliament for further consideration under the ordinary legislative procedure;
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- 1. Calls upon the European Commission to increase its investments in:
 - a. investigation of new forms of energy production and storage,
 - b. improving the efficiency of pre-existent green technologies;
 - 2. Invites the Member States to increase the funding of corporations such as firefighter and forest guard corps that work directly on the protection of forests and landscapes;
 - 3. Further calls upon the European Commission to finance the upgrading of public transportation systems in the EU by:
 - a. improving the conditions of the vehicles,

- b. acquiring more vehicles that use green sources of energy;
4. Requests the European Commission to fund institutional advertising campaigns to raise awareness about the impacts of climate change;
5. Proposes Member States to give tax benefits to companies that:
 - a. use a larger ratio of recycled materials in their production,
 - b. embrace the transition to digital means instead of paper;
6. Asks the Member States to lower the [Value Added Tax \(VAT\)](#)¹ for products that:
 - a. are sold second-hand,
 - b. are sold in local commerce;
7. Recommends the European Commission to create a tax for imported products proportional to their carbon footprint;
8. Suggests the European Commission to create an annual contest to reward green architecture projects in each Member State;
9. Supports the European Environment Agency (EEA)² in monitoring the progress of the Member States in order to reach carbon neutrality;
10. Urges the European Commission to establish legislation towards the 2050 Long Term Strategy³.

¹ The **Value Added Tax, or VAT**, in the European Union is a general, broadly based consumption tax assessed on the value added to goods and services.

² The **European Environment Agency, or EEA** is an EU agency responsible for providing independent data and producing assessments on a wide range of topics related to the environment to both policymakers and the general public.

³ The **2050 Long-Term Strategy** expresses the EU's aim to be the first carbon-neutral continent by 2050.

Motion for a Resolution by the Committee on Human's Rights (DROI)

With the COVID-19 posing a big challenge for many of Europe's healthcare systems and disproportionately affecting vulnerable communities such as refugees, their access to medical care is further hindered by practical obstacles such as language barriers and improper reception facilities. What measures should be taken by the Member States to safeguard the physical and mental healthcare needs of asylum seekers, and to also ensure unhindered access to other essential services following their arrival in the EU?

Matilde Cancela (PT, Delegate), Maria Joanico (PT, Delegate), Lazar Tripinović (RS,
Chairperson)

The European Youth Parliament,

- A. Conscious about the 9.4% [Gross Domestic Product \(GDP\) recession](#)¹ and increased unemployment rate in Member States caused by the pandemic,
 - B. Points out the [lack of an EU-wide policy](#) on dealing with non-residents' health concerns during the pandemic,
 - C. Aware of the [Member States' concerns](#) about their economic capacity to host refugees and asylum-seekers,
 - D. Concerned with the [inability of non-residents to seek medical help](#) in some Member States in times of a pandemic,
 - E. Draws attention to the [Draft Global Action Plan 'Promoting the Health of Refugees and Migrants'](#) that emphasises the importance of the healthcare needs of refugees and migrants,
 - F. Alarmed by the potential rise in [nationalistic feelings](#), as a consequence of the lack of medical equipment and the pandemic-caused economic challenges across the EU countries,
 - G. Noting the potential clash of interests between European Commission's [New Pact on Migration and Asylum](#) due to the difficulty in the relocation of asylum seekers from a Member State to another;
1. Urges the Member States to respect the established treaties ratified by the European Union and its Member States, that protect the rights of asylum seekers, including but not limited to the:
 - a. Asylum Procedures Directive²,

¹ **Gross Domestic Product (GDP) recession** is when a nation's economy experiences negative GDP, rising levels of unemployment, falling retail sales, and contracting measures of income and manufacturing for an extended period of time.

² The **Asylum Procedure Directive** is the treaty signed by the EU on regulating the asylum-seeking process.

- b. Universal Declaration of Human Rights³,
 - c. New Pact on Migration and Asylum⁴;
- 2. Proposes the European Commission to implement a common EU strategy regarding legalising the registration of migrants and asylum seekers, on the example of Portugal, in order to meet the necessary facilities to tackle physical and mental health concerns during the pandemic;
- 3. Encourages the supply of better medical and sanitary services and equipment to refugees and migration centres, including when relocating to another country during the pandemic;
- 4. Suggests the creation and enhancement of a National Refugee Council (NRC)⁵ in every Member State in order to ensure:
 - a. transparency and independence,
 - b. the extension of the monitoring policy of the European Council on Refugees and Exiles⁶ over the NRCs,
 - c. the needs of all Member States are met through the existence of the appropriate NRCs departments;
- 5. Appeals for the extension of the COVID-19 non-refundable one-time support⁷ to include the refugee and migrant population to tackle the economical and health difficulties;
- 6. Requests the Member States to allocate a higher portion of funding to the aid of asylum seekers.

³ The **Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)** is the UN's document from 1948, widely accepted as the fundamental norms of human rights that everyone should respect and protect for the first time in human history spelled out basic civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights that all human beings should enjoy.

⁴ The **New Pact on Migration and Asylum** is the European Commission's overview of new policies and approaches to migration and asylum in the EU.

⁵ The **National Refugee Council** is the national body which works on protecting and improving the rights of the refugees, asylum-seekers and displaced persons.

⁶ The **European Council on Refugees and Exiles** is the network which protects and improves the rights of refugees, asylum-seekers and displaced persons.

⁷ The **COVID-19 non-refundable one time support** is a practice of many European countries in order to help the citizens cope with the economic struggles that the pandemic brought.

Motion for a Resolution by the Committee on Culture and Education (CULT)

The COVID-19 pandemic has affected educational systems worldwide, leading to the near-total closures of schools, universities, and colleges with over 100 million children falling below the minimum proficiency level in reading as a result of the health crisis. What measures can be taken by the Member States to ensure that the youth will receive the best academic level possible during the pandemic?

Elizavet Papaconstantinou (CY, Delegate), Giorgio Papaconstantinou (CY, Delegate), Vasco Sousa (PT, Delegate), Beatriz Soares (PT, Chairperson)

The European Youth Parliament,

- A. Conscious that the current digital education system is [not able to respond](#) to student's needs,
 - B. Deeply alarmed by the [growing educational disparities](#) between students' access to digital education based on socio-economic reasons,
 - C. Pointing out that around [10% of European students don't have access to a quiet place to study or a personal computer](#),
 - D. Contemplating the lack of financial and technical support that is given to children from a lower socio-economic background,
 - E. Noting with satisfaction the increasing number of [Member States that provide additional digital training to teachers](#),
 - F. Concerned that the future generation of graduate students [will have considerably less experience](#) on skills that are attained on on-site learning;
1. Calls upon the Ministries of Education of Member States to adapt their educational system in order to ensure that student's academic and social needs are met, by:
 - a. surveying students and taking action based on the results of said surveys,
 - b. creating a platform that both teachers and students can use, in order to facilitate communication and knowledge sharing;
 2. Recommends Member States to further spread the usage of personal computers and access to the internet, by:
 - a. supporting organisations that reutilise and recycle digital equipment and therefore, provided to students from a poorer socio-economic background,
 - b. encouraging national technology corporations to expand their broadband service to all the population;
 3. Requests the Member States' to encourage universities to provide a small number of spots in classrooms in their campus so that students can attend digital class in a quieter and resourceful environment, while also respecting the COVID-19 safety guidelines;
 4. Calls upon the European Commission to create a free hotline designed to help younger children with technical issues;

5. Urges Member States to further develop teachers' formation by including digital training in their syllabus and hence, achieve the creation of regional centres of formation;
6. Invites Member States to encourage their universities to restructure education plans in order to:
 - a. emphasise more on quality and the development of online classes,
 - b. provide the option for students who finished their degree to attend practical classes they missed during the pandemic.

Motion for a Resolution by the Committee on Development (DEVE)

The current pandemic has highlighted the inequalities in access to medicines and vaccines for developing countries. How can the EU ensure equitable global access to the medicines and vaccines being developed to mitigate the impact of the pandemic?

Ana Sofia Faria (PT, Delegate), Paula Gomes (PT, Delegate), Alyssa Mia Taliotis (CY, Chairperson)

The European Youth Parliament,

- A. Alarmed by the deceleration of the vaccination process due to the vaccination [manufacturers' bargaining stance](#) towards developing countries,
 - B. Concerned by the retail of the COVID-19 vaccines in [private markets](#) at premium prices,
 - C. Contemplating the failings of the [COVAX initiative](#)¹ to ensure the equitable global distribution of the COVID-19 vaccines,
 - D. Aware that the [global demand](#) has exceeded the supply of the COVID-19 vaccines across the globe,
 - E. Strongly emphasising the non-existent chain production networks in order to avoid the [limited production of multiple vaccinations](#),
 - F. Noting with concern the challenges within public health systems of Low-Middle Income Countries (LMICs)², including the lack of:
 - i. [storage facilities](#),
 - ii. [trained professionals](#),
 - iii. [infrastructure](#),
 - iv. [Personal Protective Equipment \(PPE\)](#)³,
 - G. Deeply alarmed by the [new variants of the Coronavirus](#) emerging in a large number of countries leading to the lack of treatment,
 - H. Bearing in mind that the COVID-19 vaccination can only [successfully overcome the first mutation](#) of the virus,
 - I. Stressed by the fact that the current [SARS-CoV-2 vaccines have only been approved for use in people above 18 years of age](#);
1. Encourages the European Commission to ensure the existing protective measures surrounding ethical behaviour of vaccine manufacturers, with the aim of avoiding bilateral negotiations and partial interests;

¹**COVID-19 Vaccines Global Access (COVAX)** is a global initiative aiming to promote equitable access to vaccines and is led by the World Health Organisation.

²**Low-Middle Income Countries** are the countries which are defined as low-income economies or as lower-middle-income economies according to the World Bank Group.

³**Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)** is the equipment worn by healthcare professionals in order to minimize their exposure to hazards that cause serious workplace injuries and illnesses.

2. Condemns the European Commission to affirm the collaboration of vaccine manufacturers with small pharmaceutical companies in various countries to facilitate the distribution process;
3. Invites the European Commission to strengthen the COVAX initiative, by ensuring LMICs and Middle-Income Countries (MICs)⁴ are receiving a significant percentage of vaccines for their population through increased funding campaigns;
4. Further encourages the European Commission to abolish patents of existing approved vaccines, aiming toward the increase of global production sites and production;
5. Calls upon the European Committee of the Regions (CoR)⁵ to incentivise vaccine manufacturers to distribute a presented proportion of vaccines to LMICs with a tax cut advantage;
6. Suggests the European Commission elaborates a unified European vaccination plan for its Member States to maximize the production of COVID-19 Vaccines inside the European Union;
7. Requests the European Commission to raise the medical professionals available for the treatment of COVID-19 by:
 - a. promoting formations and courses directed towards them on management and treatment of COVID-19 cases,
 - b. encouraging final-year medical students to deploy to LMICs and help face the COVID-19 cases;
8. Invites the European Commission to strengthen international cooperation by:
 - a. providing LMICs with PPE and medical supplies from countries with mass production,
 - b. securing a percentage of EU vaccines for European LMICs,
 - c. donating vaccine storage facilities and distribution resources of countries with high vaccination percentages to LMICs,
 - d. supplying refrigerating mechanisms to avoid loss of vaccines doses;
9. Proposes the World Health Organisation (WHO)⁶ to encourage COVID-19 mass testing in all Member States, for better control of occurring mutations;
10. Urges the European Commission to set aside funding directed at scientific research regarding:
 - a. COVID-19 treatment by the development of new drugs and medical devices,
 - b. the development of new vaccines for the prevention of current and possible future mutations of Sars-CoV-2,
 - c. the extension of currently available vaccines for citizens under 18 years old,
 - d. the development of new COVID-19 vaccines specially developed for children;
11. Further requests the European Commission to implement educational campaigns concerning vaccine hesitancy by:
 - a. implementing formation for school teachers about vaccine development and safety,

⁴ **Middle-income countries** (MICs) are defined as economies with a gross national income (GNI) per capita between \$1,036 and \$12,535.

⁵ **European Committee of the Regions** (CoR) represents local and regional authorities, who advise new laws that affect their regions.

⁶ The **World Health Organisation** (WHO) is a specialized agency of the United Nations responsible for international public health.

- b. designating a part of school programmes to children's education on vaccine accessibility and safety;
- 12. Encourages medical and pharmaceutical institutions to provide informative booklets for visitors of hospitals and doctors' offices to sensitize citizens on vaccination;
- 13. Prompts the European Commission to launch a multilingual sensitization campaign regarding the importance of vaccination with:
 - a. street, television, radio advertisements,
 - b. short animated films for adults and children.

Motion for a Resolution by the Committee on Employment and Social Affairs (EMPL)

With the current pandemic increasing the uncertainty around citizens' incomes, the concept of a Universal Basic Income (UBI) has gained more traction. Taking into account the trials undertaken both prior to and during the pandemic, what should the stance of the EU and other European countries be towards this scheme?

Joana Costa (PT, Delegate), Artur Garcia (PT, Delegate), Leon Cummins (IE, Chairperson)

The European Youth Parliament,

- A. Fully alarmed by the lack of consideration in the EU around Universal Basic Income (UBI) as part of the [COVID-19 relief plans](#),
 - B. Alarmed by the [lack of governmental support](#) for artists amidst the COVID-19 pandemic,
 - C. Deeply concerned by the economic misconceptions around UBI [leading to inflation](#) amidst the COVID-19 pandemic,
 - D. Acknowledging Finland's two-year experiment on UBI leading to an [increase in general happiness](#) of citizens,
 - E. Disturbed by the COVID-19 pandemic causing the Member States to have an increase in:
 - i. [unemployment rates](#),
 - ii. [the poverty line](#),
 - F. Aware of the [socio-economic inequalities](#) between different social classes amongst the citizens of Member States,
 - G. Concerned by the lack of recognition of [Alaska's UBI experiment](#) leading to:
 - i. an increase in part-time work,
 - ii. no effect on employment,
 - H. Taking into consideration the [predicted evolution](#) of EU jobs in the future, including:
 - i. 37% to 69% of jobs being partly automated,
 - ii. 50% to 70% of jobs to change significantly;
1. Strongly urges the European Commission to allocate funding from the Recovery Plan for Europe¹ for further research on the implementation of UBI;
 2. Requests that Member States create UBI experimentation programmes whose participants should consist of people affected by the COVID-19 pandemic such as:
 - a. entertainers,
 - b. citizens fallen under the poverty line;

¹ **The Recovery Plan for Europe** is the largest stimulus package that has ever been created within an EU budget, totaling 1.8 trillion euros with the purpose of rebuilding a post-COVID Europe and making Europe both greener and more digital in turn.

3. Calls upon the European Commission to fund the creation of educational programmes in cooperation with [Unconditional Basic Income Europe \(UBIE\)](#)² to inform citizens on the benefits of UBI;
4. Directs the European Parliament to acknowledge the beneficial findings of UBI studies from:
 - a. Finland,
 - b. Alaska;
5. Proposes that the European Commission introduces UBI as a potential method for reducing the poverty gap in Europe post-COVID;
6. Advises that Member States encourage companies to increase the ratio of human workers to automated machinery.

² The **Unconditional Basic Income Europe (UBIE)** is an international non-profit organisation that has members from over 30 European countries who advocate for the implementation of UBI across Europe and that it be recognised as a Universal Human Right.

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